

Supplementary Table: Obtained records of mangrove forests in Vietnam

Period	A summary	Citation
2021	30-year observation of mangrove forest in Vietnam from space. http://www.p-gis.com/2018/10/30-year-observation-of-mangrove-forest.html . Accessed: 02/10/2021.	(Do, 2021)
2010	Measurements of total mangrove ecosystem carbon storage, global epicenter, development, and diversity to confirm the total carbon storage that maybe emitted upon deforestation of mangroves and deciding whether or not mangroves are suitable for the REDD+ strategy. Despite unclear mechanisms of loss, the results concluded mangroves a strong candidate for the REDD+ project, particularly if the strategy can be applied to facilitating adaptation to climate change and mitigation	(Donato et al., 2010)
2014	Global Forest Resources Assessment 2015 - Country Report for Vietnam	(Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2014)
2020	Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020 - Country Report for Vietnam	(Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2020)
2016	Consideration of four approaches addressing the conflicting policy objectives regarding mangrove forest loss to ensure sustainable livelihoods and biodiversity conservation.	(Friess et al., 2016)
2021	Shrimp productivity in different provinces in Vietnam. https://www.gso.gov.vn/px-web-2/?pxid=V0658&theme=N%C3%B4ng%20%C3%A2m%20nghi%E1%BB%87p%20v%C3%A0%20th%E1%BB%A7y%20s%E1%BA%A3n . Accessed: 02/10/2021.	General Statistics Office, 2021)
1999	The Rule for Land use and Natural resource utilization. Decision no.116/1999/QĐ-TTg of May 3rd, 1999. Ratifying the zoning plan for Restoration of Mangrove forest in Ca Mau, Bac Lieu, Soc Trang and Tra Vinh provinces.	(Government of Vietnam, 1999)
2020	Exploring the reasons for the success or failure of conservation and restoration projects to develop a more robust approach. The report stated improved monitoring, a defined protocol, and a co-management approach with strong community participation is needed.	(Hai et al., 2020)
2013	An analysis of mangrove forest coverage in eight countries under the influence of commercial aquaculture. Results showed aquaculture may have been responsible for the displacement of more than half of total mangrove loss.	(Hamilton, 2013)
2010	An analysis of mangrove forest coverage in eight countries under the influence of commercial aquaculture. Results showed aquaculture may have been responsible for the displacement of more than half of total mangrove loss.	(Hawkins, 2010)
1993	An insight into the potential, the geographical distribution, the diverse functions, and the physio-chemical characteristics of mangrove ecosystems to understand the important cultural and economic benefits they provide.	(Hong & San, 1993)
2013	Assessing the value of direct and indirect ecosystem services provided by Can Gio's mangroves through earth-observation-based mapping and extensive household surveys. According to the results, related occupations with the least knowledge about mangrove benefits also expressed the least willingness to further protect them.	(Kuenzer & Tuan, 2013)

2011	An evaluation of the potential for mangrove carbon projects in Vietnam. A total of 8 distinct conclusions, accompanied by proper contexts and solutions, were made.	(McNally et al., 2011)
2014	Coastal forest protection and development plan to respond to climate change for the period 2015–2020	(Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2014)
2020	The Socialist Republic of Viet Nam Updated Nationally Determined Contribution	(Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, 2020)
2018	An investigation of the usability of machine learning techniques to estimate the aboveground biomass of mangrove plantation at a coastal area of Hai Phong city. Results showed an increase in accuracy.	(Pham et al., 2018)
2021	An analysis of the Vietnamese government's claim that the stakeholder participation in REDD+ has been improved over the course of 2011-2019, focusing exclusively on level of interest, engagement and influence in REDD+ policy events. Findings show that despite the framework on REDD+ has demonstrated Vietnam's initial political commitment to improve inclusive decision making, momentum has been lost over time.	(Pham et al., 2021)
2019	An in-depth analysis on the knowledge gap, the opportunities and the constraints for mangrove management in the Red River Delta provinces. The report encouraged a shift in policy of land-use planning as well as enhancement in local participation in mangrove forest protection through a combination of transparent benefit-sharing and inclusive decision-making solutions.	(Pham et al., 2019)
2018	A discussion of the domestic situation of carbon pricing in Vietnam, as well as the importance of issuing forest carbon certificate to forest protectors so that local communities can increase their income while sustaining the natural forests. Results indicate that one hectare of secondary broad-level forest in Vietnam can accumulate more than twice that of old-growth forest.	(Tran & Tamotsu, 2018)
2012	Economic analysis of value of ecosystem services. A component research project in a large-scale project “Ecosystem Services for Climate Resilience in Quy Nhon City”, funded by Rockefeller Foundation and coordinated by ISET, USA	(Tran et al., 2012)
2015	Major development milestones and the current status of seed production and farming of marine shrimp in Vietnam. Despite the intensifying characteristic of shrimp farming, large areas of improved extensive shrimp farming system may continue to be maintained for sustainable development.	(Tran et al., 2015)
2014	Usage of remote sensing to quantify the rate of mangrove shoreline changes for a 58 years period confirmed that erosion and accretion are significant, further proving its importance in predicting and planning to minimize losses and reduce threats to coastal development as well as human safety.	(Tran et al., 2014)
2019	A discussion of the principle factors influencing mangroves in Vietnam as well as successful management practices and models for mangrove restoration. In-depth investigation showed a historical lack of sufficient regulatory mechanisms for the protection of mangroves and concluded difficulty in predicting the future state of mangroves in Vietnam due to the patchy data available at the time.	(Veettil et al., 2019)
2013	An object-based classification approach for estimating the percentage of mangroves to assist the government to monitor the extent of the shrimp farming area. The method	(Vo et al., 2013)

provides continuous forest fraction without utilizing auxiliary information on ownership structures.

- 2015 Establishing a framework for linking remotely sensed data, household survey data and geophysical data to estimate the values of mangrove ecosystem services in Ca Mau province. Due to the absence of primary data, the report was only able to include a partial estimate of the total value. (Vo et al., 2015)
- 2020 An estimation of the direct and indirect monetary values of ecosystem services in the Can Gio mangrove forests by using a combination of data retrieved from remote sensing and household surveys. (Yen & Khoi, 2020)
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